

PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING MEDICAL TERMINOLOGIES.

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Особенности преподавания медицинской терминологии.
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Abstract. Language and medicine are two of the most important aspects in the life of mankind. And the language in medicine plays a decisive role in the health of all mankind. A huge responsibility lies with the medical translator when translating certain terms. But no less great responsibility lies with the teacher of a medical translator. Teaching, on its own, is not an easy profession, with the amount of responsibility that cannot be overestimated. Doubly complicating the task of the teacher of the future translator is the huge number of lives saved. If the doctor is the messenger of God on earth, then their interpreters are angels. In this article, I would like to touch on a very non-obvious, but necessary topic - the features of teaching medical terms.

Аннотация. Язык и медицина – два важнейших аспекта в жизни человечества. А язык в медицине играет решающую роль в здоровье всего человечества. Огромная ответственность лежит на медицинском переводчике, при переводе тех или иных терминов. Но не менее большая ответственность лежит и на учителе медицинского переводчика. Преподавание, в отдельности, представляет собой не легкую профессию, с количеством ответственности которую невозможно переоценить. Вдвойне усложняют задачу преподавателя будущего переводчика это огромное количество спасенных жизней. Если доктор это посланник Бога на земле, то переводчики их ангелы. В этой статье мне бы хотелось затронуть весьма неочевидную, но нужную тему – особенности преподавания медицинских терминов.

Keywords: English for special purposes, Medical English, medical terminology, professional communication.

Ключевые слова: английский язык для специальных целей, медицинский английский язык, медицинская терминология, профессиональная коммуникация.

Today, many healthcare professionals are learning medical English: some want to train or work abroad, others dream of traveling to international conferences, and still others want to be the first to read publications about discoveries in medicine. Consequently, there are some difficulties in working with students, who study a foreign language for special purposes. Firstly, it is the fact that the time for preparation can be seriously limited. Secondly, specific requests and needs of students create additional difficulties for the teacher, which are associated with the actualization of English language in the field of highly specialized professional communication.

This situation often requires from the teacher to develop creative materials, which will be up to the academic needs of students. The solution of such problems are caused by the specificity of the professional field and the individualization of approaches to education is possible by attracting various authentic medical documents in English — newsletters for

patients, medical questionnaires, video materials and brochures in English that are distributed in medical institutions in English-speaking countries with the purpose of educational work among population, in English-language medical sites and television shows, which allow people to have a healthy lifestyle. All of these resources are extremely valuable for developing this type of course.

We consider the issues of studying medical terminology in the lessons of the English language with a foreign audience. Medical terminology is a macrotermino system consisting of subsystems, each of which has its own characteristics. This phenomenon must be considered in creating a system of tasks and exercises for teaching English as a foreign language to medical students.

Listening is a mandatory component of any English as a foreign language lesson. We present the possible topics and options for working with anatomical and clinical terminology. We conclude that teaching the language of the specialty for medical students should be diverse, multidisciplinary and include work to realize three main aims: teaching, developing and educational.

In professional context, in the methodology of teaching English language for special purposes to medical students, it is important to know and understand all the features of medical terminology.

Work with professional vocabulary goes through the following stages:

- 1) presentation of new vocabulary;
- 2) formation of lexical skills;
- 3) the organization of conditions to review new vocabulary.

Scientific and technical literature is characterized by the use of terminological units. Hundreds of thousands of words and word-combinations belong to the terminological systems of science, technology, trade, law, sports. These linguistic units are not used or even understood by people outside the particular specialty. Every field of science or activity has its specialized vocabulary.

Every profession or field has its own jargon, i.e. a registered or a specialised language that allows for quick and efficient communication smoothly between members of the same discipline. Practitioners of medicine and health sciences have their own jargon or particular language for medicine. Medical terminology is a specialised language used by learners, specialists and experts of medicine and health sciences. It is regarded as one of the most difficult language among all the other specialised languages in different fields. Medical language includes very complicated long terms which seem difficult to sound, spell, remember and even understand e.g. amonasehydrocharideoympphaeoid, encephalomyeoneuropathy, dermatomucosomyositis, etc.

Kenneth and Chuntana Methold (1975:6) argue "medical writing relies very heavily on a specialised vocabulary. most of these words cannot be usefully translated or even defined. Medical writing is often so difficult to understand, it is necessary to approach it from a variety of angles if one is to understand the ideas hidden in long words and even longer and complex terms."

Further, medical language provides unfamiliar and strange words, for example some words contain triple (o) together as in hysteraplingoophorectomy and others start in double (o) as in oophorectomy.

Furthermore, the grammatical patterns in medical context are different, for instance the plural is formed by another way different from that one in an ordinary English, many nouns do not add "-s" or "-es" in the plural, but change in vowels or the last part of the words e.g. amoeba / amoebae, bacterium / bacteria, phenomenon / phenomena, protozoon / protozoa, fungus / fungi, curriculum / curricula, etc.

Medical terminology is not commonly taught separately, but rather as incidental to clinical studies. Acquiring medical terminology will occur concurrently along with the vast body of clinical information that students must assimilate. Students develop some grasp of medical terminology through repeated encounter, inference and memorization, but this thesis considers these learning methods inherent in common practice both inefficient and insufficient

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